

QUTB KOORDINATALAR SISTEMASIDA UCHBURCHAK YUZINI HISOBLASHNI MATEMATIK MODELI

N. I. To‘xtasinova

Farg‘ona davlat universiteti
Matematika kafedrası
o‘qituvchisi

I. Mirzaabdullayev

Farg‘ona davlat universiteti
Matematika yo‘nalishi 1 – kurs
talabasi

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada dekartd koordinatalar sistemasida ishlanish yo‘llari mavjud va murakkab bo‘lmagan ayrim masalalarni Qutib koordinatalar sistemasida berilishi va ishlanish yo‘llari hamda uning matematik modelini ishlab chiqish bo‘yicha na‘munalar va tavsiyalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Dekart koordinatalar sistemasi, Qutb koordinatalar sistemasi, masala, vektor, uchburchak, kenglama.

Tekislikda Dekart koordinatalar sistemasi - Tekislikda biror O nuqtada kesishuvchi o‘zaro perpendikulyar 2 ta o‘qni olamiz. Bu o‘qlarning har birida O nuqtadan boshlab birlik vektorlarni ajratamiz. Musbat yo‘nalishlari mos ravishda \vec{i}, \vec{j} vektorlar bilan aniqlanuvchi 2 ta o‘qdan tashkil topgan sistema tekislikda **To‘g‘ri burchakli koordinatalar sistemasi** deyiladi. O nuqta koordinatalar boshi \vec{i}, \vec{j} vektorlar esa ortogonal va birlik vektorlardir.

Ox, Oy o‘qlar mos ravishda absissalar va ordinatalar o‘qi deyiladi. To‘g‘ri burchakli koordinatalar sistemasida har doim avvalo nuqtaning absissasi, keyin esa ordinatasi belgilanadi.

Endi quyidagi masalani hal qilaylik:

Masala 1. Dekart koordinatalar sistemasida uchlari $A(x_1; y_1), B(x_2; y_2), C(x_3; y_3)$ nuqtalarda bo‘lgan uchburchak yuzini toping?

Yechish: Buning uchun koordinata tekisligida uchlari $A(x_1; y_1)$, $B(x_2; y_2)$, $C(x_3; y_3)$ nuqtalarda bo'lgan istalgan uchburchakni qaraymiz. Keyin esa bizga ma'lum bo'lgan turli xil shakl yuzalari ustida almashtirishlar bajarib quyidagi ifodalarni hosil qilamiz:

$$S_1 = (x_1 + x_3)(y_3 - y_1)/2 \quad (\text{chizmadagi trapetsiya yuzi})$$

$$S_2 = x_1 \cdot y_1 \quad (\text{chizmadagi to'g'ri to'rtburchak yuzi})$$

$$S_3 = (x_2 - x_1)(y_1 + y_2)/2 \quad (\text{chizmadagi trapetsiya yuzi})$$

$$S_4 = (y_2 + y_3)(x_3 - x_2)/2 \quad (\text{chizmadagi trapetsiya yuzi})$$

$$S_5 = x_3 \cdot y_3;$$

(S_5 yuza chizmada hosil bo'lgan eng katta to'g'ri to'rtburchak yuzi)

$$S_x = S_5 - (S_1 + S_2 + S_3 + S_4)$$

(S_x yuza biz qidirayotgan ΔABC yuzi)

Bu ifodalarni soddalashtirib quyidagi formulaga ega bo'lamiz:

$$S_x = \frac{1}{2} \cdot |[x_1 \cdot (y_3 - y_2) + x_2 \cdot (y_1 - y_3) + x_3 \cdot (y_2 - y_1)]| \quad (1)$$

Qutb koordinatalar sistemasi - Tekislikda biror O nuqtani OL nur va bu nurda yotuvchi $OA = \vec{i}$ birlik vektorni olamiz. Agar tekislikda olingan OL nurni Ox o'q deb olinsa va \vec{i} vektorni O nuqta atrofida Oy o'qidagi \vec{j} birlik vektor ustiga tushirish uchun qisqa yo'l bo'yicha burish soat strelkasi xarakteriga teskari bo'lsa, u holda koordinatalar sistemasi musbat orientatsiyali, tekislikni esa orientatsiyalangan deyiladi. Hosil qilingan geometrik obraz *qutb koordinatalar sistemasi* deyiladi. U odatda $R = \{O; \vec{i}\}$ ko'rinishida belgilanadi. O nuqta qutb boshi, OL nur qutb o'qi deyiladi. M nuqtaning tekislikdagi holati ikkita son: biri $|\vec{i}| = 1$ birlik kesma yordamida o'lchangan $\rho = |OM|$ masofa, ikkinchisi OL va OM nurlar orasidagi $\varphi = (\vec{i}; \vec{OM})$ burchak bilan to'la aniqlanadi. ρ masofa M nuqtaning *qutb radiusi* deyiladi.

Nuqtaning Dekart va Qutb koordinatalar sistemalari orasidagi bog'lanishi Tekislikda (O, \vec{i}) qutb koordinatalar sistemasi berilgan bo'lsin. Koordinatalar boshi qutb boshi bilan, absissalar o'qining musbat qismi qutb o'qi bilan ustma-ust tushadigan musbat orientatsiyali (O, \vec{i}, \vec{j}) dekart reperini kiritamiz. M

nuqtaning qutb koordinatalari r, φ , dekart koordinatalari esa x, y bo'lsin. O'z navbatida M nuqtaning qutb koordinatalari r, φ ni uning dekart koordinatalari x, y orqali topish mumkun:

$$r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}, \quad \operatorname{tg} \varphi = \frac{y}{x}, \quad \varphi = \arctg \frac{y}{x}, \quad (2)$$

$$x = r \cdot \cos \varphi; \quad y = r \cdot \sin \varphi; \quad (3)$$

(2) formulani Dekartdan Qutb koordinatalar sistemasiga o'tish, (3) ni esa Qutb koordinatalar sistemasidan Dekart koordinatalar sistemasiga o'tish formulasi deyiladi.

Endi quyidagi masalani qaraylik:

Masala 2. Qutb koordinatalar sistemasida uchlari $A(r_1; \varphi_1)$, $B(r_2; \varphi_2)$, $C(r_3; \varphi_3)$ nuqtalarda bo'lgan uchburchak yuzini toping?

Yechish:

Istalgan ko'pburchak yuzi uni tashkil qiluvchi bir-birini qoplamaydigan ko'pburchaklar yuzalari yig'indisiga teng. Yuqoridagi chizma bo'yicha ΔABC yuzini topamiz. Uning qiymati quyidagiga tengligi ravshan:

$$\Delta S_{ABC} = \Delta S_{AOC} - (\Delta S_{OBC} + \Delta S_{OBA}) \quad (4)$$

Uchburchakning 2 tomoni va ular orasidagi burchagi berilganda uning yuzi:

$$\Delta S_{AOC} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot |\vec{r}_3| \cdot |\vec{r}_1| \cdot \sin(\varphi_3 - \varphi_1) \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta S_{OBC} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot |\vec{r}_3| \cdot |\vec{r}_2| \cdot \sin(\varphi_3 - \varphi_2) \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta S_{OBA} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot |\vec{r}_1| \cdot |\vec{r}_2| \cdot \sin(\varphi_2 - \varphi_1) \quad (7)$$

formulalardan topilishi bizga ravshan.

Endi har bir ifodani o'z o'rniga qo'yib soddalashtirsak :

$$\Delta S_{ABC} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot |\vec{r}_3| \cdot |\vec{r}_1| \cdot \sin(\varphi_3 - \varphi_1) - \left[\frac{1}{2} \cdot |\vec{r}_3| \cdot |\vec{r}_2| \cdot \sin(\varphi_3 - \varphi_2) + \frac{1}{2} \cdot |\vec{r}_1| \cdot |\vec{r}_2| \cdot \sin(\varphi_2 - \varphi_1) \right]$$

$$\Delta S_{ABC} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot [|\vec{r}_3| \cdot |\vec{r}_1| \cdot \sin(\varphi_3 - \varphi_1) + |\vec{r}_3| \cdot |\vec{r}_2| \cdot \sin(\varphi_2 - \varphi_3) + |\vec{r}_1| \cdot |\vec{r}_2| \cdot \sin(\varphi_1 - \varphi_2)] \quad (8)$$

(8) formulaga ega bo'lamiz.

(8) Formula uchlari $A(r_1; \varphi_1)$, $B(r_2; \varphi_2)$, $C(r_3; \varphi_3)$ nuqtalarda bo'lgan uchburchak yuzini topish formulasi deb ataladi.

Bizga trigonometriya kursidan malumki, quyidagi qo'shish formulalari o'rinlidir:

$$\sin(\varphi_3 - \varphi_1) = \sin \varphi_3 \cos \varphi_1 - \sin \varphi_1 \cos \varphi_3$$

$$\sin(\varphi_2 - \varphi_3) = \sin \varphi_2 \cos \varphi_3 - \sin \varphi_3 \cos \varphi_2$$

$$\sin(\varphi_1 - \varphi_2) = \sin \varphi_1 \cos \varphi_2 - \sin \varphi_2 \cos \varphi_1$$

Aynan shu masalani yuqorida isbotlab chiqqan (1) formula bo'yicha ishlab chiqsak :

Avval uchburchakning har bir koordinatalarini dekart koordinatalar sistemasiga o'tib biz isbotlagan (1) ga qo'yib, yuqoridagi trigonometrik formulalarni qo'llab kerakli shakl almashtirishlar bajarilsa ham (8) formulaga kelib qolishi aniq va ravshandir.

XULOSA: Dekart koordinatalar sistemasida uchlari

$A(x_1; y_1)$, $B(x_2; y_2)$, $C(x_3; y_3)$ nuqtalarda bo'lgan uchburchak yuzi:

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \cdot [|x_1 \cdot (y_3 - y_2) + x_2 \cdot (y_1 - y_3) + x_3 \cdot (y_2 - y_1)|];$$

Qutb koordinatalar sistemasida uchlari

$A(r_1; \varphi_1)$, $B(r_2; \varphi_2)$, $C(r_3; \varphi_3)$ nuqtalarda bo'lgan uchburchak yuzi:

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \cdot [|\vec{r}_3| \cdot |\vec{r}_1| \cdot \sin(\varphi_3 - \varphi_1) + |\vec{r}_3| \cdot |\vec{r}_2| \cdot \sin(\varphi_2 - \varphi_3) + |\vec{r}_1| \cdot |\vec{r}_2| \cdot \sin(\varphi_1 - \varphi_2)]$$

formulalardan topiladi.

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